

USER TUTORIAL

RADx Data Hub Tutorial Introduction and Overview

Overview

The NIH Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics Data Hub (RADx Data Hub) is a centralized data repository that provides access to analytic tools and de-identified COVID-19 data from the RADx Initiative. The RADx Data Hub better supports scientific efforts to understand COVID-19 and factors associated with disparities in morbidity and mortality in underserved and vulnerable populations, by allowing researchers to discover, access, and perform analyses of COVID-19 datasets in a cloud-enabled platform.

Introduction

This tutorial provides in-depth, step-by-step instructions on how to use the features and functionality of the RADx Data Hub most effectively. If you still have questions after reading the tutorial, consult some of the other support documentation (e.g. the Frequently Asked Questions page or the Glossary) or reach out directly by using the “Contact Us” link in the main navigation bar or the footer.

Target Audience

The primary audience for this tutorial is external researchers. Internal NIH staff should consult the appropriate Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) on the Resource Center page.

The Features of the RADx Data Hub

The RADx Data Hub contains several different features to help you get the most out of the system and better meet your research needs. These include:

- **Common Page Navigation Tools:** The RADx Data Hub features navigation tools (e.g. the navigation bar, the footer) that will lead you to different pages and features within the Hub.
- **Home Page:** The Home page is a one-stop shop for many of the key resources on the RADx Data Hub. From this page, you can quickly reach educational documents (e.g. the Frequently Asked Questions [FAQ], the User Tutorial), get information on news, funding opportunities, events, and study updates, search for studies, and view statistics on the information in the Hub.
- **Study Explorer:** The Study Explorer contains a number of discovery features (e.g. search, sorting, filtering) to help you quickly and easily search across studies to find datasets of interest and learn more about variables contained therein.
- **Study Overview Pages:** Each study in the RADx Data Hub has its own Study Overview page, which contains study metadata, variables, data files, and downloadable documents.

- **Variables Overview Pages:** Each variable in the RADx Data Hub has its own Variable Overview page, which contains detailed variable information and a list of studies containing the variable. By viewing these pages, you can understand the data’s context and structure before you request access—helping you make informed decisions with confidence.
- **Variables Catalog:** This tabular resource lists all variables in each data file for each study. By viewing this resource, you can gain a deeper understanding of the key variables in a study to help you determine whether it aligns with your research goals before requesting access to the study.
- **Support Resources:** The system gives you multiple ways to submit a support request, so you can ask questions, report bugs, and request in-depth assistance from the Support team on complex questions. You can use the “Need Support?” link in the navigation bar or in the footer.
- **User Registration:** To access certain features, such as the Approved Data tab, you will need to first register with the RADx Data Hub. After you have registered, you can login using the “Login” button in the top-right of every page to access role-based features.
- **Approved Data:** After you have been approved for data, you can access the “My Approved Data” tab. From here, you can apply for a workbench instance, download data, or transfer it to your workbench instance.
- **Public Data:** The Public Data page has synthetic data files, which you can practice using our “Analytics Workbench” feature.

Study Explorer

General

The publicly available Study Explorer lets you search RADx study metadata to find studies for your research. In the Study Explorer, you can:

- [View available RADx Data Hub studies](#)
- [Perform free-text searches](#)
- [Navigate results](#)
- [Refine results through sorting and filtering](#)
- [Perform cross-entity search across studies and variables](#)

View Available RADx Data Hub Studies

To view available RADx Data Hub studies and variables, click “Study Explorer” in the upper navigation bar. You will be taken to the Study Explorer. It has two tabs: Studies and Variables. By default, the Studies tab is displayed first, where you can see all findable RADx Data Hub studies, presented, by default, in Table View.

Study Explorer

Home / Study Explorer / Studies

Search for studies and variables.....

Search

List Table

Filters

Study Population Focus

Cohort Size Range

Study Domain

Study Design

Data Collection Method

NIH Institute / Center

RADx Data Program

Has Data Files

Study Variables

Studies (183)

Variables (87)

1 - 50 of 183 Results

Show: 50 Sort by: Study Name Ascending

List of Variables	Study Name	dbGaP Study Accession	Study Population Focus	Estimated Cohort Size	Study Domain	Study Design	Data Collection Method	NIH Institute / Center	RAI Proc
	2183 SARS-CoV-2 Rapid Antigen Test	phs002682	N/A	488	Medical Device or Tool Development; Point-of-Care (POC) Testing; Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT)	Device Validation	Survey; Antigen Testing Device	NIBIB	RAI
	A Community Health Worker Intervention to Identify and Decrease Barriers to Pre-Procedural COVID-19 Testing Among Los Angeles County Department of Health Safety-Net Patients	phs002920	Adults; Older Adults or Elderly; Underserved or Vulnerable Populations; Racial or Ethnic Minorities; Hispanics or Latinos; African Americans	128	Testing Rate or Uptake; Pandemic Perceptions or Decision-Making; Vaccination Rate or Uptake; Virological Testing	Interventional or Clinical Trial	Interview or Focus Group; Survey	NLM	RAI
	A Community-Led Approach to Enhance COVID-19 Testing Among Vulnerable Latinos	phs002660	Adults; Older Adults or Elderly; Hispanics or Latinos	4312	Social Determinants of Health; Diagnostic Testing	Longitudinal Cohort	Survey; Interview or Focus Group	NIDA	RAI

Figure 1: Study Explorer Link in the Navigation Bar and default Study Explorer View with Studies and Variables Tabs

In the top right of each tab you will find several controls (Figure 2) including:

- *Studies and Variables tab* that allows you to switch between study and variable search
- *List/Table View toggle* that allows you to switch between List View (which presents results in a vertically arranged list) and Table View (which presents results in a tabular format)
- *Download Results button* downloads the search results as a csv file
- *Manage Columns button* allows you to choose columns to hide or show.

Figure 2: View and Download Results Controls

Performing Free-Text Searches & Viewing Search Results

You can perform free-text searches by entering custom queries in the search bar. To perform a free-text search in the Study Explorer:

1. Click "Study Explorer" in the navigation bar
2. Locate the Search bar (Figure 3)
3. Enter your free-text query
4. Press "Enter" or click the magnifying glass icon to view results, sorted by relevance based on your query

Tip: You can also search from the Home Page

Figure 3: Study Explorer Search Bar

Navigate Through Search Results

After performing a search, use the page navigator in the top right of the Study Explorer to move through search result pages (Figure 4). To navigate through pages of the results, you can:

- *Option 1: Click the Forward or Backward Arrows in the Page Navigator* to move one page forward or one page backward in the results.
- *Option 2: Click Individual Page Numbers* (typically in the format: 1, 2, ... X) to go to an individual page.

Figure 4: Page Navigator

In addition to changing the search results view, you can also change the number of results per page. To do this, click the “Show” dropdown at the top or bottom right (Figure 5). Then, select the number of results to show per page, and the page will automatically update.

Figure 5: "Number of Results per Page" and Sorting Controls

The same controls are available on the Variables tab, but the sorting options are going to be different (Figure 6).

Figure 6: "Number of Results per Page" and Sorting Controls on the Variables tab

Refining Results Through Sorting and Filtering

Sorting and filtering search results can further refine a search.

To sort in the Study Explorer:

1. Locate the sorting options in the top right. (Figure 5)
2. Pick either "Ascending" or "Descending" in the sort order dropdown
3. Use the sort by dropdown to select a field for sorting, and results will dynamically update.

Filtering is more complex than sorting but can help further refine a search. The filter pane is made up of two primary components: filter categories and filter values. Filter categories (e.g. "Has Data Files" or "RADx Data Program") are high-level buckets that include multiple filter values. Filter values are the specific criteria by which you can filter search results. For example, the filter values in the "Has Data Files" category are "Yes" or "No."

Three techniques to narrow or refine a search using filters:

Technique	Description	Example
Select One Filter Value	Selecting a single value in a Filter Category will filter the results by that value.	If you click "Yes" under "Has Data Files", you will only see studies with data files.
Select Multiple Filter Values in One Filter Category	Selecting two or more values within one filter category will function as a Boolean 'OR.'	If you click "RADx-UP" and "RADx-rad" within "RADx Data Program", you will see studies that align to either program
Select Multiple Filter Values Across Filter Categories	Selecting two or more values across two or more filter categories will narrow your search and function as a Boolean 'AND.'	If you click "RADx-UP" from "RADx Data Program" and "Yes" under "Has Data Files", you will see studies that are aligned with RADx-UP AND have data files.

Table 1: Different Search Techniques

After deciding a filtering technique, select values by expanding the accordion for the desired filter category (Figure 7). Next, click the checkbox next to the filter value, and results will dynamically update.

To remove a single filter value, click the checkbox a second time or click the "X" button on the filter badge above the filter pane. To remove all filters, press "Reset Search" above the filter pane.

Note: The numbers to the right of the filter values represent the number of results a selected value will return.

Figure 7: Filter Box

Performing Cross-Entity Searches

Two tabs of the Study Explorer allow users to perform cross-entity searches. That is, you can search for studies or variables, and the results will display linked studies/variables.

For example, if you want to search for studies focused on Essential workers, you select “Essential Workers” value in the “Study Population Focus” filter, and your search returns the 12 studies focused on this particular population.

In the Studies tab, you can see the variables for a particular study by clicking the “View list of variables” icon next to that study (Figure 8).

Figure 8: View list of Variables icon next to the study name

System will display list of variables contained in this study's files (Figure 9).

Figure 9: List of Variables modal

Using the Variables Tab to search will give variables related to your search term. For example, if you wanted to see what variables are related to age, you would enter age, and it would generate a list of all variables related to age across all studies.

Similarly to the Studies Tab, in the Variables Tab, you will see the same icon (Figure 8). But clicking on it will expand the list of studies, where files contain that particular variable (Figure 10).

Studies (87)

Explore studies in search

- A Community-Led Approach to Enhance COVID-19 Testing Among Vulnerable Latinos
- A Confectionary-Based Screening Tool for Assessing Chemosensory Loss in COVID-19 Patients
- A Data Science Approach to Identify and Manage Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C) Associated with SARS-CoV-2 Infection and Kawasaki Disease in Pediatric Patients
- A Handheld Microchip for GC Analysis of Breath to Screen for COVID-19
- A Nurse-Community Health Worker-Family Partnership Model: Addressing Uptake of COVID-19 Testing and Control Measures
- Adapting Community-Based Task-Shifting for the COVID-19 Response Among Underserved Populations in Piedmont, North Carolina (ACT UP)
- Addressing COVID-19 Testing Disparities in Vulnerable Populations Using a Community JITAI (Just in Time Adaptive Intervention) Approach-A UHealth CTSA Program
- AFS/SERS Saliva-Based SARS-CoV-2 Earliest Infection and Antibodies Detection
- AICORE-kids: Artificial Intelligence COVID-19 Risk AssEssment for kids
- Assessing Testing Strategies for Safe Return to K-12 Schools in an Underserved Population
- Back to ECE Safely with SAGE: Reducing COVID-19 Transmission in Hispanic and Low-Income Preschoolers
- C2SPARC: Implementing Mobile, POC COVID-19 Testing in Partnership with a Community-Based Organization to Reach Women Who Use Drugs
- Characterization of Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children and Its Relationship to Kawasaki Disease
- Collaborative Community Networks to Optimize Implementation of Low Barrier COVID-19 Testing Efforts Among Diverse Latinx Populations in Northern California
- Communities Fighting COVID!
- Communities Fighting COVID!: Returning Our Kids Back to School Safely
- Community Collaboration to Combat Coronavirus (C-COVID)

Figure 10: List of Studies modal

Both modals have a button “Explore studies/variables in search”. Clicking this button will bring you to a respective tab of the Study Explorer populated with search results for this study/variable.

Study Overview

Each study has an overview page, which contains key documents, metadata, and variable and file information. To reach the Study Overview page, locate a study in the Study Explorer or Variables Catalog and click on the “Study Name”.

On the Study Overview page, you can:

- [View study information](#)
- [View variable information](#)
- [Learn how to request study access](#)
- [Download publicly available documents](#)
- [Learn about data files and download resources](#)

View Study Information

Study Overview contains comprehensive study information, it begins with the study name, and below that, a Study Information section lists several attributes to help you gain a high-level understanding of the study.

Study Information

dbGaP Study Accession: [phs002682](#)

NIH Institute/Center: NHLBI

RADx Data Program: RADx Tech

Release Date: 2022-08-12

Updated Date: 03/28/2023

Study Description: There are two device studies under the 2183 banner. The 2183b study uses an enhanced visual display compared to the original study (2183a), so it has been renamed. These prospective clinical studies seek to examine the performance of the 2183 device (a and b), a lateral flow immunoassay for the point-of-care (POC) detection of SARS-CoV-2 nucleocapsid protein antigen, compared to the Roche 6800 Cobas PCR for SARS-CoV-2 assay. The goal of the 2183b study is for EUA approval for the device to be used among symptomatic persons by trained healthcare personnel collected mid-turbinate specimens. Note: no device performance data will be included in the data files.

Principal Investigator: Gibson, Laura

Has Data Files: Yes

Study Domain: Medical Device/Tool Development; Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT); Point-of-Care (POC) Testing

Study Design: Device Validation Study

Data Collection Method: Antigen Testing Device; Survey

Keywords: Near Patient Testing

Multi-Center Study: Yes

Study Sites: UMass Chan Medical School and Northwestern University

Data Types: Clinical; Questionnaires/Surveys

Study Start Date: 10/16/2020

Study End Date: 11/06/2020

Species: Human Data

Estimated Cohort Size: 488

Acknowledgement Statement: This study was supported through funding, 75N92020C00020, from the National Heart Lung and Blood Institute (NHLBI) as part of the RADx Tech program. Operations support and data management occurred primarily through the UMass Chan Medical School's Center for Clinical and Translational Science, Clinical Studies Core, and the Department of Population and Quantitative Health Sciences. Additional recruitment of participants occurred at Northwestern University. Data collection occurred through the Eureka Platform managed by the UCSF team. Quest Diagnostics ran the standard comparators (Roche 6800 Cobas PCR for SARS-CoV-2 assays). Approved users should acknowledge the provision of data access by dbGaP for accession phs002682.v1.p1, and the NIH RADx Data Hub. Approved users should also acknowledge the specific version(s) of the dataset(s) obtained from the NIH RADx Data Hub.

NIH Grant or Contract Number(s): 75N92020C00020

Consent/Data Use Limitations: General Research Use

Figure 1: Overview Page

View Variable Information

The Variable Information section provides the total number of unique variables across all data files for the study. It also provides a list of all variable names and labels with a link to the specific Variable Overview page if available so users can easily access detailed variable information.

Learn How to Request Study Access

Request study data access, including harmonized and non-harmonized data file access in dbGaP. Click the How to Request Access button in the top right of the Data Files section to view an expandable data access checklist. Navigate to the [Request Data Access](#) section of the tutorial to learn more.

Data Files						
How to Request Access						
Total Files: 6		Data Files: 2	Metadata Files: 2	Dictionary Files: 2		
File Name	File Type	File Format(s)	# of Records	# of Variables	Metadata	Dictionary
project60_DATA_transformcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Harmonized	csv	187	162		
project60_DATA_origcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Non-harmonized	csv	187	169		

Figure 2: How to Request Data Access button

Download Documents

The Study Overview page contains downloadable, publicly available documents. There are two ways to download documents (Figure 2):

- *Option 1 - Download Individual Documents:* To download a single document, press the download icon in the download column on the documents table. The document should appear in the browser's download center for you to open or save.
- *Option 2 - Download All Documents:* To download all documents, press "Download All" in the upper right of the documents section. A zip file with all study documents will appear in the browser's download center for you to open or save.

Study Documents			
Download All			
Document	Document Name	File Size	Download
Read Me	project2_README_v1.html	281.25 KB	

Figure 3: Download Functionality in Documents Table

Learn About Data Files and Download Resources

The Data Files section has downloadable metadata and data dictionary files and viewable variable information to help you learn more about a study and its data, before requesting access.

In the Data Files table, data and supporting files are organized by bundles. Specifically, each bundle contains a metadata and data dictionary file, aligned to a harmonized or non-harmonized data file.

While you cannot download original or transformed files from the Study Overview Page, you can download associated metadata and data dictionary files. To do this, click the download icon in either the Metadata or Dictionary columns (Figure 4). The file will show up in the browser's download center for you to open or to save.

Tip: For studies with lots of data files, use sorting to locate a file more quickly. Click a column header once to sort in ascending order and twice for descending.

Data Files						
Total Files: 6			Data Files: 2	Metadata Files: 2	Dictionary Files: 2	
File Name	File Type	File Format	# of Records	# of Variables	Metadata	Dictionary
project60_DATA_transformcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Harmonized	csv	187	162		
project60_DATA_origcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Non-harmonized	csv	187	167		

Figure 4: Data Files Table

You can view metadata files in an easy-to-read, interactive tool called the Metadata Viewer, powered by CEDAR. To access the Metadata Viewer, click on the eye icon in the Data Files table. This will open a window that lists several different metadata attributes in the file. To the right of each label are help tips, which contain metadata attribute descriptions. Additionally, you can expand accordions to see more metadata attribute information.

Figure 5: Metadata Viewer

View information on data file-based variables by clicking the carrot in the “Number of Variables” column (Figure 6). This will open a table, to view the data file variables.

Data Files						
Total Files: 6			Data Files: 2	Metadata Files: 2	Dictionary Files: 2	
File Name	File Type	File Format	# of Records	# of Variables	Metadata	Dictionary
project60_DATA_transformcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Harmonized	csv	187	162		
				Variable Names nih_record_id, nih_age, alcohol_date_mdy, nih_alcohol_frequency, nih_sex, nih_asthma, nih_atc_sub_abuse, nih_autism, nih_cancer_past_yr, nih_chronic_kidney_disease, nih_chronic_lung, nih_copd, nih_cardiovascular_disease, nih_depression, nih_diabetes, nih_hypertension, nih_immunocompromised, nih_iv_drug_use, nih_other_chronic_cond, nih_mental_health_disorder, nih_sickle_cell_disease, consent_given, consent_recontact, consent_mdy, cov_pan_chal_hib_2, cov_pan_chal_med_2, cov_pan_chal_trans_2, cov_pan_chal_2, covid_pandemic_challenges_abod_2, covid_pandemic_challenges_food_2, covid_pandemic_challenges_waste_2, covid_vaccine, nih_employment, nih_education, employed_ew, employed_healthcare_2, family_income, flu_vaccine_season_3, flu_vaccine_season_2, gender_identity_term_2, nih_insurance, hi_loss_covid, hitstat_date_mdy, household_congregate_3, household_famgen_3, household_homeless, housing_concerns, housing_date_mdy, isolate_maintain_job, jobless_covid19_2, language_english, language_home__1, language_home__2, language_home__3, language_home__4, language_home__5, language_home__6, language_home__7, language_home__8, language_home__9, language_home__90, language_home__99, nih_lifetime_use_alcohol, med_iv_date_mdy, positivemonth_covidtest_2		
project60_DATA_origcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Non-	csv	187	167		

Figure 6: Variables Information in the Data Files Table

Variables Overview

General

Each variable present in the study files in the system has an overview page, which contains comprehensive variable information. To reach the Variable Overview page, you must locate a variable in the Variables Tab in the Study Explorer, in the Variable Information section on a Study Overview page, or in the List of Studies on the Studies tab in the Study Explorer, and click on the “Variable Name” hyperlink.

On the Variable Overview page, you can:

- [View detailed variable information](#)
- [View a list of studies using the variable](#)

View Variable Information

The Variable Information section lists several attributes to help you gain a detailed understanding of the variable. At the bottom of the page you can find a scrollable list of studies using the variable.

The following attributes are provided for each variable.

- Label: The descriptive variable name.
- Section: Overarching grouping of the variable.
- Data Type: The type of data stored in the variable. Either an integer, float, or string.
- RADx Variable Category: The level of harmonization in relation to the RADx programs. For a full definition, see the [RADx Variable Category glossary entry](#).
- Description: The detailed variable description. This includes more information about the variable including how it was collected, it was harmonized if applicable, and relevant notes.
- Keywords: Synonyms or related terms.
- Term: The ontological term related to the variable.
- From: The RADx program(s) the variable was used in.
- Permissible Values: A table detailing the allowed values for the variable and corresponding labels.

Variable Information

Label	Abdominal pain												
Section	Symptoms												
Data Type	integer												
RADx Variable Category	RADx Core Variable												
Description	<p>The nih_abdom_pain data element records responses to the prompt, or a congruently meaning prompt, "Abdominal pain". Equivalent prompts are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Abdominal Pain" RADx-UP - "Abdominal pain" RADx-rad - "Stomach or abdominal pain" RADx-DHT <p>The values for this data element are integers that come from a list of 5 permissible integer values.</p> <p>The nih_abdom_pain data element is the result of the harmonization of other RADx program data elements: covid_abpain RADx-UP; abdominal_pain RADx-rad; dht_abdom_pain RADx-DHT</p> <p>Note that the meaning of the value 97 is context specific and depends on the subset of permissible value used by a specific study (not all studies presented the full set of permissible values documented here for this data element). Therefore, the meaning of the value 97 in an individual data record MUST be determined by referring to the original data dictionary for the non-harmonized data in that study.</p>												
Keywords	abdominal pain												
Term	[SYMP:0000457] abdominal pain												
From	RADx-DHT dht_abdom_pain RADx-UP covid_abpain_2 RADx-rad abdominal_pain												
Permissible Values	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Value</th> <th>Label</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>97</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>98</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>Prefer not to answer</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Value	Label	0	No	1	Yes	97	Other	98	Don't know	99	Prefer not to answer
Value	Label												
0	No												
1	Yes												
97	Other												
98	Don't know												
99	Prefer not to answer												

Figure 1: Variable Overview Page

List of Studies Using Variable

The List of Studies Using Variable section lists all the studies that contain the specified variable to help you identify relevant datasets. Each study is linked to its Study Overview page where you can find more study information.

Variables Catalog

General

The Variables Catalog is publicly available and displays study data file variables as a comma-separated list. With the Variables Catalog, you can quickly understand a study's variables to make a more informed decision when requesting study data access. To reach the Variables Catalog, click the link in the top navigation bar.

Figure 1: Variable Catalog Link in the Navigation Bar

Once on the Variable Catalog:

1. [Find and view variable information](#)
2. [Navigate to the RADx and Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes \(dbGaP\) Study Overview Pages](#)
3. [Download catalog content as a CSV file](#)

View Variable Information

View variable information in the Variable Catalog (Figure 2) in two ways:

1. *All Variables* lists out all data file variables in a comma-separated list
2. *RADx Core Variables* lists RADx Core variables and labels in a tabular format

Figure 2: Variables Catalog Toggle

To switch between views in the table select the radio button next to the view you are interested in. After selecting an appropriate view, search for variables, studies, and more using your browser's "Find" feature (CTRL/CMD + F).

Navigate to RADx and dbGaP Study Overview Pages

In the Variables Catalog, access the RADx Data Hub and dbGaP Study Overview pages by clicking the following links:

1. The *Study Name* links to the RADx Data Hub Study Overview page, where you can gain a better understanding of study metadata

2. The *dbGaP ID (PHS ID)* leads to the dbGaP Study Overview page, where you can request study-level access

To get a complete Data Variable Report with multiple views of the RADx data variables, including per-variable frequency counts and dbGaP (PHS) IDs:

[Download Complete Report in Excel](#)

All Variables RADx Core Variables

Last Updated: June 7, 2024

Search for variables...

RADx Program	Study Name	dbGaP ID	File Name	Variables
RADx Tech	2183 SARS-CoV-2 Rapid Antigen Test	phs002682	dictionary_origcopy_2023-03-28_v1.csv	ID, LABEL, Datatype, Enumera

Figure 3: Links to the RADx Data Hub and dbGaP Study Overview Pages

Download Report

In addition to viewing the Variables Catalog, you can also download variable information as a CSV file. Click “Download Complete Report in Excel” to get the Data Variable Report with multiple views of the RADx data variables, including per-variable frequency counts and dbGaP (PHS) IDs

Figure 4: Download Complete Report

User Support

General

The Support Team can answer questions for various topics, such as technical issues and bugs, questions about analytics tools, feature requests, and more. You can reach our support team by using the support form, which is available from any page in the application. To contact our support team, follow these steps:

1. Create a support request clicking “Need Support?” on the navigation bar or in the footer. This will redirect you to the User Support Request Form.

RADx® Data Hub

Figure 1: "Need Support?" Link in Navigation Bar

2. Complete the required fields, indicated with an asterisk

The image shows a support request form with the following fields and labels:

- All fields marked with asterisk (*) are required.
- * Email: Text input field
- * Full Name: Text input field
- * Institution: Dropdown menu
- * Request Type: Dropdown menu
- * Request Title: Text input field
- * Request Detail: Text area
- Submit: Button

Figure 2: Support Request Form

3. Choose the appropriate option under "Request Type" to route the request

Figure 3: Request Type Dropdown

- *General Feedback* - Provide Data Hub site feedback
 - *Technical* - Report bugs or other technical problems
 - *Feature Request* - Provide new feature suggestions
 - *Engagement* - Request a RADx Data Hub training, presentation, or demonstration
 - *Workbench Support* - Request help on the Analytics Workbench
4. Under “Request Title,” briefly describe the request
 5. Provide specific details about the request under “Request Details”
 6. Click “Submit” to complete the support request. You will receive an automated email confirming the Support Team received the request. This will include the ticket number and any further instructions. Soon after submission, a member of the Support Team will contact you with further questions or possible resolutions.

User Registration

Create an Account

To create a RADx Data Hub account, you need a [Researcher Auth Service](#) (RAS) Identity Provider (IdP) account, specifically an [NIH Login](#) or [eRA Commons](#) account. Once you have an account with either IdP, you can register with the RADx Data Hub following the steps below:

1. To register, click “Login” in the top right corner on any RADx Data Hub page. The system will display a modal with a Login/Sign Up using RAS button (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Login Modal

2. Press “Login/Sign-Up Using RAS,” and you will be directed to the RAS Sign-In page (Figure 2).

Figure 2: RAS Login Page

3. Enter your eRA or NIH Login credentials, and the system will redirect you to the RADx Data Hub User Registration page. (Figure 3).

User Registration

[Home](#) > [User Registration](#)

All fields marked with asterisk (*) are required.

* **First Name** * **Last Name** * **M.I.**

* **Email**

ORCID ID # * **Job Title/Position**

Learn more at: <https://orcid.org/>

* **Institution**

Don't see your institution? [Click here to add an institution](#)

Figure 3: User Registration Form

4. Fill in the required fields. The system automatically displays First Name, Last Name, Middle Initial (M.I.), and Email, based on your RAS information. If these are incorrect, please contact RAS.
5. Click the Institution dropdown and add an institution. If you cannot find your institution, press “Click here to add an institution,” fill out the required fields (Figure 4), and press “Add Institution.” After that, the institution should appear in the Institution dropdown.

Figure 4: Add Institution Form

- Carefully read the Terms and Conditions (Figure 5), and click the provided box to accept conditions.

Figure 5: Terms & Conditions

- Press “Submit” to finish registering. The system will automatically log you in, redirect you to the Home page, and send an email confirming the registration.

Note: RADx Data Hub leverages dbGaP to manage study access. When registering for the RADx Data Hub, users register using the same RAS credentials used for dbGaP (or a linked account). Failure to do this will make it impossible for the system to show your authorized studies available in “My Approved Data.”

Login to the RADx Data Hub

1. Click “Login” in the top right corner on any RADx Data Hub page. The system will display an additional modal with a Login/Sign Up option (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Login/Sign-Up Modal

1. Press “Login/Sign-Up Using RAS,” and you will be directed to the RAS sign-in page (Figure 2).

Figure 2: RAS Sign-In Page

2. Select the NIH Login or eRA option and enter login credentials. The system will redirect you to the home page after correctly entering your credentials.

Note: If you have a login.gov account linked to an NIH Login or eRA account used for dbGaP, you may use that to login.

Request Data Access

Requirements

The RADx Data Hub requires eRA Commons authentication and dbGaP authorization to access controlled data. Data requestors must have an eRA Commons (or NIH login) account with PI status to submit a request. Non-PIs must have a PI submit a request in dbGaP on their behalf. Once the PI is granted data access, the PI can grant team members access by logging into dbGaP and adding them as a downloader.

Important notes

- Your eRA* or NIH Login used for dbGaP **must match** your RADx Data Hub login.
 - *Users should use an eRA account, if possible*
- Non-PIs must have an [eRA account](#) to be added as a data downloader

Resources:

- [eRA Commons Frequently Asked Questions \(FAQs\)](#)
- [eRA Help and Tutorials](#)
- [NIH / eRA Helpdesk / Ticketing System](#)

Requesting Access to Studies

To gain study data access, including harmonized and non-harmonized data files, PIs must request [dbGaP](#) access.

1. Log into the RADx Data Hub using your **dbGaP eRA or NIH Login**.
2. Locate a study through the **Study Explorer**, and click on the **Study Name** to view the Study Overview page.

The screenshot shows the 'Study Explorer' page with a search bar and a table of results. The table has the following columns: Study Name, dbGaP Study Accession, Study Population Focus, Estimated Cohort Size, Study Domain, Study Design, Data Collection Method, NIH Institute / Center, RADx Data Program, and Has Data Files. The first row is highlighted with a red box.

Study Name	dbGaP Study Accession	Study Population Focus	Estimated Cohort Size	Study Domain	Study Design	Data Collection Method	NIH Institute / Center	RADx Data Program	Has Data Files
2183 SARS-CoV-2 Rapid Antigen Test	phs002682		488	Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT); Point-of-Care (POC) Testing; Medical Device/Tool Development	Device Validation Study	Antigen Testing Device; Survey	NHLBI	RADx Tech	Yes

*Note: To request access to more than one study, record the **dbGaP Study Accession** of each study. Later, you will search for and add the **dbGaP Study Accession IDs** of interest in dbGaP.*

3. Click on the **dbGaP Study Accession** link in the Study Info box on the Study Overview page. This will bring you to the dbGaP Study Overview page.

The screenshot shows the 'Study Overview' page for '2183 SARS-CoV-2 Rapid Antigen Test (0.510 MB)'. The 'Study Information' section is visible, with the 'dbGaP Study Accession: phs002682' link highlighted by a red box.

Study Information
dbGaP Study Accession: phs002682
NIH Institute/Center: NIBIB
RADx Data Program: RADx Tech
Release Date: 08/12/2022
DOI: 10.60773/54ae-xy13
Updated Date: 04/09/2024

4. In dbGaP, submit a **data access request** for the study(ies). Use dbGaP's Important Links and Information section for guidance.

*Note: To request access to more than one study, add datasets by navigating to the "Choose Datasets" tab of the Project Request, and type in the **dbGaP Study Accession IDs** for each study individually.*

NCBI Site map All databases PubMed Search

dbGaP genotypes and phenotypes

Browse/Search Authorized Access Help

Beacon My Projects My Requests Downloads Downloaders My Profile

Project Request

OMB control number: 0925-0670 Expiration date: March 31, 2016

Project Details Research Project Collaborators IT Director **Choose Datasets** Confirm Datasets Review DUC Review DUL Review Applications Feedback

Please select datasets to request access to. If you have changed any common information (research statement, list of collaborators), all approved application and those being reviewed by DAC(s) will need to be resubmitted.
For any study that has more than one consent group, there are no overlaps in subjects between the consent groups.

Filter Consents

Primary disease Molecular data type Study design

Approved for GRU Approved for commercial use Approved for method development Health biomedical research

Study accession Exclude IRB required

Consent Group Data Use Limitations Participants DAR Status

- Once you receive a study access confirmation email from dbGaP, return to the RADx Data Hub. Login using the **same eRA or NIH Login as for dbGaP**, and navigate to **My Approved Data**.

Study Explorer Variables Catalog Helpful Information Contact Us Data Access Internal

Public Data **My Approved Data**

RADx® Data Hub

The NIH Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics Data Hub (RADx Data Hub) is a centralized data repository that provides access to analytic tools and de-identified COVID-19 data from the RADx Initiative. The RADx Data Hub supports scientific efforts to better understand COVID-19 and factors associated with disparities in morbidity and mortality in underserved and vulnerable populations, by allowing researchers to discover, access, and perform analyses of COVID-19 datasets in a cloud-enabled platform.

Search for Studies... Search

About the RADx Data Hub Learn more about the RADx Data Hub

User Tutorial For those who are new to the RADx Data Hub, we highly recommend taking a moment to explore the comprehensive RADx Data Hub Tutorial

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) Browse the collection of answers to frequently asked questions about the RADx Data Hub

Resources:

- [dbGaP: Apply for Controlled Access Data Video](#)
- [dbGaP: Frequently Asked Questions \(FAQs\)](#)
- [dbGaP Helpdesk](#)
- [Tips for Preparing A Successful Data Access Request](#)

Adding Downloaders

Downloaders must meet the following requirements **prior** to the PI adding them as a downloader:

- Have an eRA Commons account

- Have logged into dbGaP at least once

After gaining data access, the PI (data request submitter) must log back into dbGaP and:

1. Navigate to the **Downloaders** tab under Authorized Access

NCBI Site map All databases PubMed Search

db GaP genotypes and phenotypes

Browse/Search Authorized Access Help

Beacon My Projects My Requests Downloads **Downloaders** My Profile

Downloaders

Find user: First name Last name

The prerequisites to be chosen as a downloader:

- 1. Have an eRA Commons account or a NIH email account. The eRA account doesn't need to have a PI role.
- 2. Successfully logged into the dbGaP Authorized Access System at least once.

Downloaders on your projects:

Project	Remove Role
	<input type="button" value="X"/>

2. Use the First and Last name boxes to search for the downloader

3. Select a team member's name, and add them to the project using **Set Downloader**

NCBI Site map All databases PubMed Search

db GaP genotypes and phenotypes

Browse/Search Authorized Access Help

Beacon My Projects My Requests Downloads **Downloaders** My Profile

Downloaders

Find user: First name Last name

The prerequisites to be chosen as a downloader:

- 1. Have an eRA Commons account or a NIH email account. The eRA account doesn't need to have a PI role.
- 2. Successfully logged into the dbGaP Authorized Access System at least once.

Give downloader role to:

First Last

Email:

Phone:

Organization(s):

For project(s):

After the PI adds a team member as a downloader, the team member will receive a welcome email from dbGaP. Then, the team member can login into the RADx Data Hub **using the same dbGaP eRA account as in dbGaP**, and navigate to **My Approved Data**.

Resources:

- [Assign Downloaders for dbGaP Data Video](#)
- [RADx Data Hub Support Request](#)

My Approved Data

General

My Approved Data allows you to access data files based on your Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP) approvals. This page will group files into one table per study. Within each study table, the files are organized by bundles, which is a set of files including a data file, metadata file, and data dictionary (along with any SAS file equivalents if available).

After accessing My Approved Data, you can:

- [Download approved data files](#)
- [Apply for Workbench add-ons](#)
- [Create a workbench instance with one of the available tools \(JupyterLab, Data Wrangler, or SAS\)](#)
- [Add files to your workbench](#)

Note: My Approved Data will be empty until you are approved to access to at least one RADx Data Hub study in dbGaP.

Figure 1: My Approved Data Link in Navigation Bar

Download files

To download files:

Option 1 - Select a Bundle: To select a bundle, check the box next to a harmonized or non-harmonized data file. This will select the high-level data file and its supporting files (i.e., metadata and data dictionary files)

Option 2 - Select an Individual File: This process varies for supporting files (e.g., metadata and data dictionary files) and data files. To select a metadata or data dictionary file, check the box next to the file name. To select an individual harmonized or non-harmonized file, first check the box next to the file name. This will select the entire bundle. Then, deselect the metadata and data dictionary files

Option 3 - Select All Files: Click the “Select All” button. This will select all study table files

After selecting the desired files, you can click “Zip & Download,” and the files will appear in your browser’s download center as a zip file, which you can save or open.

Figure 2: Selection Functionality and “Zip & Download” Button

Apply for Add-Ons

After registering, you will automatically have the default Workbench access, which includes JupyterLab and RStudio but does not include Data Wrangler or SAS Viya. To access those tools, apply for a Workbench Add-on.

1. Press “Apply for Add-on” (Figure 3). The system will direct you to a separate page displaying the request form

Figure 3: “Apply for Add-On” Button

2. Fill out the required fields

Requestor Information

Name: Samuel Waddell | Email: waddell_samuel@bah.com | Institution: RADx Radical

Application Information

* Primary Interest in Workbench: Select... | Other Interest in Workbench: [Text Field]

* Analytics Software Request: [Dropdown] | Are you affiliated with a RADx program (C)DCC? I am affiliated with a RADx program (C)DCC

* Research Use Statement: [Text Area] | * Reason for Request: [Text Area]

Terms of Service Agreement

Please read the following Terms of Service, and enter your name below to agree to the Terms of Service and submit your request.

[Download the Terms of Service](#) | * Agree to the Terms of Service: Enter your name here to agree... | Submit

Figure 4: Add-On Application Form

3. Download and read the Terms of Service. Type your name in the “Agree to the Terms of Service” field if you agree
4. Press “Submit.” The RADx Data Hub team will review the request and email you if you are approved for a Workbench Add-on

Note: There are a limited number of licenses available for SAS and Data Wrangler. The licenses are distributed on a first-come, first-serve basis. You may only hold one license at a time.

Create A Workbench

To create a workbench, press “Create Workbench.” In the future, press “Launch Workbench” to access an existing workbench.

Figure 5: “Create Workbench” Button

Add Files to Workbench

To add approved files to a workbench, select the file or files to transfer. Then, click “Add to Workbench” in the top right of the study table (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Add to Workbench Button

Public Data

General

The Public Data page contains synthetic data files. Prepared using mock data, these files allow you to test analytics workbench offerings and capabilities before using real research data.

You must log into the Data Hub to access the Public Data page. After logging in, you will see a “Data Access” dropdown in the navigation bar. You can click “Public Data” to go to the Public Data page.

RADx® Data Hub

Figure 1: “Public Data” Link in the Navigation Bar

Once on the “Public Data” tab, you can:

- [Download public data files](#)
- [Create or launch a workbench](#)
- [Transfer files to your workbench](#)

Download Files

To download files, select one or multiple files using one of following techniques:

Option 1 – Select an Individual File: To select a single file, click the checkbox icon next to the file name.

Option 2 – Select Multiple Files: To select multiple files, click the checkbox next to the files.

Option 3 – Select All Files: Click “Select All” to select all files within the table.

After selecting files, click “Zip & Download,” and the files will appear in your browser’s download center as a zip file to save or open. The “Zip & Download” button will be greyed out until you select a file.

Figure 2: Selection Functionality and “Zip & Download” Link

Create and Launch a Workbench

To launch the workbench, you can press the “Create Workbench” button on the Public Data page, which will automatically route you to the workbench application. After creating a workbench, you can go back to your workbench instance by pressing the “Launch Workbench” button (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Launch Workbench Button

Transition Files to Workbench

After creating a workbench instance, you can transfer files to the workbench. To add files to a workbench, you can first select the file or files you want to transfer. Then, press the “Add to Workbench” button to transfer them to your workbench instance (Figure 4).

Figure 4: “Add to Workbench” Button

Workbench Tutorial

General

The Analytics Workbench allows you to launch compute instances with Jupyter notebooks, using Python or R, in a personal workspace environment. Workbench add-ons include 1) Data Wrangler, a no-code data transformation, analysis, and visualization option and 2) SAS Viya Analytics Pro, a cloud-hosted SAS environment that allows scalable computing, data storage, and usage tracking to enable data access, transform, analysis, visualization, and mapping capabilities.

Note: There is a limited number of licenses available for SAS and Data Wrangler. The licenses are distributed on a first come first serve basis.

Jupyter Lab General

Figure 1: Labeled Jupyter Notebook Interface

The main elements of JupyterLab editor are:

1. **Notebook:** A document containing analysis code, outputs, and any additional markdown or text.
2. **Cell:** A single section of a notebook where to enter code, markdown, or text.
3. **Toolbar:** Perform the most common notebook actions, including:
 - Save
 - Insert cell below
 - Cut selected cell
 - Copy selected cell
 - Paste from clipboard
 - Run selected cell
 - Interrupt the kernel
 - Restart the kernel
 - Restart the kernel and run all cells
 - Change cell type (i.e. Code, Markdown, Raw)
 - Launch terminal
4. **Environment:** Displays the current notebook kernel type
5. **File Browser:** Displays lists of folders, notebooks, and other files

- The Personal Studio environment is a private, personal Amazon EFS directory
6. **Left sidebar:** Contains tabs to access the following functionalities:
- **File Browser:** Displays lists of folders, notebooks, and other files
 - **Running Terminals and Kernels:** View current kernels and terminals running in JupyterLab. Optionally shut down all or select resources (i.e., notebooks, terminals, kernels, apps, and instances)
 - **Git:** Connects to a Git repository for Git tool and operation access
 - **Table of Contents:** Automatically generated for each notebook, Markdown file, or Python file open to navigate the document's structure with clickable entries
 - **Extension Manager:** Enables and manages third-party JupyterLab extensions
 - **Jupyter AI:** A JupyterLab tool to explore generative AI models and integrate them into notebooks

Create and Launch a JupyterLab Space

The default workspace environment is a ml.t3.medium (2 vCPU, 4 GiB memory) instance type.

To create a new JupyterLab space:

When the Workbench is launched, select "JupyterLab" from the "Overview" section, or select "JupyterLab" from the "Applications" in the left panel (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Workbench Applications Highlighting JupyterLab

Select "+ Create JupyterLab space" in the upper right corner of the JupyterLab page

- In the "Create JupyterLab space" dialog, specify a name for the space in the "Name" field. To finish, click "Create space."
- **Note:** Because the platform is shared, workspaces must have a unique name. If the workspace name already exists, the following error will appear at the bottom of the page (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Error Message for Workspace Name Exists

To launch a JupyterLab space:

1. From the Workbench Home page, select “JupyterLab” from the Overview section, or select “JupyterLab” from “Applications” in the left panel (Figure 2).
2. Select “Run” in the Action column of the JupyterLab space to start the workspace (Figure 4). This may take up to a minute to start.

Figure 4: Start Running JupyterLab Space

3. Once the status changes to “Running”, select the “Open” icon in the Action column to launch JupyterLab in a new tab (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Open JupyterLab Space

To create a new notebook:

1. From the landing page, select “File,” “New,” and “Notebook” (Figure 6).
 - In the “Select Kernel” dialog, select a kernel on the dropdown menu. To finish, click “Select”, which launches the notebook.

Figure 6: Launch Notebook from File Menu

2. From the Launcher page, click a preferred kernel in the Notebook section (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Launch Notebook Using Launcher

Upload and Download Files

To upload files from a local machine into a JupyterLab space:

1. In the left sidebar, choose the "File Browser" icon
2. In the File Browser, choose the "Upload Files" icon
3. Select the files to upload and choose "Open"
4. Once the file appears in the home folder, double-click the file to open it in a new tab

To download a file locally:

1. In the left sidebar, choose the "File Browser" icon
2. Right click the file and select "Download"

To Download an entire file locally:

1. From the menu, choose "File," "New," and "Terminal", which will launch a Terminal in a new JupyterLab tab
2. Type the following command replacing `folder_name` and `/path/to/folder: zip -r -X folder_name.zip /path/to/folder`
3. Once the folder is zipped and it appears in the File Browser, right click the .zip file and select "Download"

Clone a Git Repository

Git repositories can be cloned into the JupyterLab home folder using the following steps:

1. Select the Git icon in the left sidebar.
2. Choose "Clone a Repository."
3. In the Clone Git Repository window, enter the Git URL (for example, <https://github.com/aws/amazon-sagemaker-examples.git>)
4. Under "Project directory to clone into," enter the path to the local directory where the cloned directory should exist, otherwise Studio will clone the repository into the home directory.
5. Choose "Clone," which will automatically open a new terminal window and clone the repository. This may take up to a minute depending on the repository size.
6. If the repository requires credentials, a prompt will appear to enter a username and personal GitHub account access token.
7. When complete, the File Browser will open, displaying the cloned repository.
8. Choose the Git icon to view the Git user interface, which tracks the repository.
9. To track a different repository, open the repository in the file browser and click the Git icon.

Create a Persistent Conda Environment

Environments can be customized by installing and removing extensions and packages as needed. Any installed extensions and packages installed on the environment will persist. To create persistent conda environments in the JupyterLab application, use the following steps:

1. Open a JupyterLab space.
2. From the landing page, select "File," "New," and "Terminal".
3. Within the terminal, create a new conda environment, replacing myenv with the desired environment name:
`conda create -n myenv`
4. Activate the environment
`conda activate myenv`
5. Install any necessary packages for the environment, for example:
`conda install numpy pandas`
6. Install the ipykernel to create a kernel option. This step can be skipped if it has already been installed:
`conda install ipykernel`
7. Add the new conda environment to the Jupyter kernel, changing the `--display-name` option as preferred:
`python -m ipykernel install --user --name myenv --display-name "MyEnvironment"`

8. Verify installation of the kernel:
`jupyter kernelspec list`
9. When a notebook is launched, the new kernel should appear. If the kernel is not listed, close the tab and reopen the JupyterLab space

Access Public Data

To access curated public and synthetic datasets on the RADx Data Hub's Data Access page, follow the [Public Data Tutorial](#)

Datasets from the [AWS Registry of Open Data](#), an AWS-hosted repository of more than 400 publicly available datasets, can be copied into a JupyterLab environment using the following steps:

1. Identify a dataset of interest and find the associated Amazon Resource Name (ARN).
 - For example: [NIH NCBI Sequence Read Archive \(SRA\)](#)
 - ARN: `arn:aws:s3:::sra-pub-src-1`
 - The bucket name is `sra-pub-src-1`
2. From the JupyterLab landing page, select “File,” “New,” then “Terminal.”
3. Enter the following command: `aws s3 sync s3://sra-pub-src-1 .`
4. Replace `sra-pub-src-1` with a selected dataset bucket name

Change Environment

Notebooks launch with the minimum instance type available by default. The minimum instance type is appropriate for most tasks, however, a larger instance can be requested by submitting a [Support Request](#). Follow the instructions in the [User Support Requests Tutorial](#) and select “Workbench Support” when choosing a Request Type. Please provide as much detail as possible in the request for the support team to determine the best suitable environment. For more detailed information about available instance types and their performance capabilities, see [Available Studio Instance Types](#).

File Sync

If an added Workbench file does not appear in the File Browser of JupyterLab, the workspace should be resynced. Close the JupyterLab tab, and refresh the My Approved Data page. Then, follow the steps to relaunch the JupyterLab page. If the files still do not appear, the workspace may need to be manually synced with the following steps:

1. From the File menu, click “File,” “New,” and “Terminal.”
2. Enter the following into the Terminal: `./s3sync.sh`

If the files in a workspace are still missing, please submit a [Support Request](#).

Data Wrangler

General

By default, Data Wrangler uses the m5.4xlarge (16 vCPU, 64 GiB memory) instance type. To request a different compute instance, please see the Change environment section. If a Data

Wrangler instance has been provisioned, a Data Wrangler flow can be created using the following steps:

1. From the Workbench Home page, select “Canvas” from “Applications” in the left panel.
2. Click “Run Canvas” to start the instance. This may take up to 8 minutes.
3. Once the instance status has changed to “Running”, click the “Open Canvas” button to launch Canvas in a new tab.
4. Select the “Data Wrangler” application in the sidebar of Canvas applications and click “Create a data flow” which will open a dialog to rename the data flow for the analysis.
5. Click import data (Figure 1) and select the data file type (i.e., Tabular or Image). Select one of the data source options from the dropdown, or upload files directly. See [Import](#) to learn more about AWS data import options.
6. Data Wrangler can now be used to add transforms, analyze, and visualize your data. To learn more, see [Transform Data](#) and [Analyze and Visualize](#).
7. To export a data flow, click Export from the data flow page. To learn more about exporting data transformations to other platforms, see [Export](#).

Figure 1: Import Data to Data Wrangler Flow

To stop running Canvas, click “Stop Canvas” on the Canvas homepage (Figure 2). Click the checkbox and the “Stop Canvas” button that appears to confirm shutdown. Be sure to save all work and data flows prior to shutdown.

Figure 2: Stop Canvas Application

SAS Viya General

Figure 1: SAS Interface

From the My Approved Data or Public Data page, a “Launch SAS” button will appear if a license has been granted. To launch the SAS platform, click “Launch SAS.”

To start a new program:

1. From the main menu, click “New”, and “SAS Program”. A new blank program will open in the work area

To save a SAS program:

1. Click the “Save” icon on the work area toolbar
2. Select the location where files will be saved
3. Enter the name of the program
4. Click "Save"

To open a SAS program:

1. Click the "Open" icon on the main menu bar
2. Find the location of the program in the left panel
3. Select the SAS program to open in the right panel
4. Click “Open” and the program will appear in the work area

To run just a portion of a SAS program, highlight the portion to run. To run the entire SAS program, no code needs to be highlighted:

1. Click the "Run" icon on the work area toolbar
2. Open the “Log” tab to confirm the program ran correctly